

COMPOSITIONAL CONSTRUCTION IN DRAMATURGY

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Abstract. *Dramaturgy always appeals to man, seeks to reveal the secrets of his soul, seeks to understand the essence of human interactions, whether human history or it doesn't matter if it's modern. He set out to study dramaturgy First of all, let's get acquainted with the odramaturgical rules and mysteries. This article or section needs sources or references that appear in credible, third-party publications. You will find the answers to the questions that need to be answered more often.*

Keywords: *Composition, pralog, expodition, course of events, conflict, Knot, culmination, solution, epiologist, fable, perepitiya, plot.*

КОМПОЗИЦИОННОЕ ПОСТРОЕНИЕ В ДРАМАТУРГИИ

Аннотация. *Драматургия всегда обращается к человеку, стремится раскрыть тайны его души, стремится понять суть человеческих взаимодействий, будь то человеческая история или не важно, современная. Он взялся за изучение драматургии Прежде всего познакомимся с одраматургическими правилами и тайнами. Для этой статьи или раздела необходимы источники или ссылки, которые появляются в заслуживающих доверия сторонних публикациях. Вы найдете ответы на вопросы, на которые нужно чаще отвечать.*

Ключевые слова: *Композиция, пралог, экспедиция, ход событий, конфликт, Узел, кульминация, развязка, эпилог, басня, перепития, сюжет.*

INTRODUCTION

It has been a century since the dramatic tour entered Uzbek literature. Ilk as a dramatic work the well-known Behbudi's "Padarkush" was written in 1911. Hundred years of history and experience This Uzbek drama has the beginning of the last century and the period of the Second World War except has always been slower than other literary genres. This is a decline especially in the so-called "stagnation period" of the last century 70 80s and in the early years of independence clearly felt. There are certain objective and subjective reasons for such delay. First of all, it is worth noting with regret that in our literature it deals only with dramaturgy private creators are rare. Borrás is also a scene of rapid discovery creating works that do not become a constant partner of theaters.

Second, the situation, even if such a talented drama is created and staged, it is a problem of attracting the audience to it is born. Third, because of the market economy, the playwright is not getting rich with his work. Yet in the last 20 years, the drama has not been left untouched, the stage has not been emptied, more or less the audience also entered the theater. The most important is the form of drama of recent years and the content has been updated, the genre possibilities have expanded. Artists world began to make effective use of the surviving experiences of dramaturgy. These years to pineapples according to which many poetic dramas were born. "Istanbul tragedy" by E.Vakhidov, by A. Aripov "Sahibqiron", "Secretary of the Messenger of Allah" by U. Kochkar, "Yusuf and Zulayha" by R. Babajan His works are written

in this way. The development and renewal of drama is a topic is evident in the expansion of the scale. A scene on a particular historical subject in this regard it should be noted that the number of works has increased. The change in attitude to history is great appreciation of the artistic, scientific and spiritual-enlightenment heritage of our ancestors, historical sources as a result of the study, our people experienced a process of self-realization.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Especially Amir Temur, In complex genres about complex historical figures such as Ahmad al-Farghani, Mashrab stage productions of various forms were born. Among them is the People's Writer of Uzbekistan Odil Yakubov's historical drama "Fatihi Muzaffar or the story of a parivash" plays an important role holds.

It should be noted that O. Yakubov is a very experienced writer in dramaturgy. In the 60's, "If I say, my tongue burns, if I don't say, my tongue burns", "My heart must burn", "China fame with dramas called "Love", "When the Apple Blossoms", "Secrets of a Home" had won. This experience and skill is at its best in the artist's latest drama gave the result. During this period, many dramas on modern themes were also born. This Erkin Khushvaqtov, Salohiddin Sirojiddinov, Usmon Azim, Sanjarali Imamov, Kholiq Khursandov, Nasrullo Qobil, Komil Avaz Toir Yunusov created effectively. From them the works of some have become a constant repertoire of theaters and quench the thirst of the audience satisfied and increased his interest in theaters. Zero theater in the spirit of spiritual enlightenment of the people has long been known to be the most effective and lively means of upbringing. The scene is real life is a mirror of evil. In this sense, E. Khushvaqtov is one of the above-mentioned playwrights especially the kid took the prize. It is more folklore-ethnographic, to the materials of folklore addressed topics that are dying in our national traditions.

E. Khushvaqtov's "Chimildiq", "Qalliq" staged one after another at the National Theater of Uzbekistan Poems such as "Game", "Red Apple", "Anxious Bride" to imbue the spirit, the essence of the steps they have taken from time immemorial, with new traditions It tries to enrich, to increase the attitude of the younger generation. They do not succeed in the methods and forms chosen to express their intention. For example, The dramas "Chimildiq" and "Qalliq Oyun" are based primarily on light-hearted events. the extreme artificiality of the relationship between, instead of elevating the value of our traditions arouses hatred. The solution in these dramas also does not satisfy the audience. 1. (92.93.96.97b.) Each artist chooses a certain thing, a theme. It's just like a fetus in it, develops in the mind, imagines the system of images, events, and cooks the idea. The next in front of him after the theme is selected by the author for the future work the problem is transverse. This problem is an example of determining the structure of a work. Of course the construction of the work, that is, the determination of its content, is also much more responsible. This is the author falls into the act of composing the composition of the work. In fact the word composition is from Latin It means structure in Uzbek.

RESULTS

The composition of the work not only with the system of events but also with the construction of words, their delivery. Because "In the works of art, only the images, the language and the stylistic means are all put forward by the author serves a specific idea. The structure of the work is the same as the above, according to the author's idea absorbed. As long as the images are not placed in a certain order the criterion and harmony between the parts in the image are

also undermined. Creativity is a skillful word of all kinds whether he is an artist or not, he is not considered to have fully achieved his idea and purpose. Mabodo is creative If the purpose, the idea, the point of view is not consistent and clear, his work is structurally sound, does not come out successfully. ”2 (4 b). Special attention should be paid to the harmony in the work. This is where every detail in the work, every element, demands each other, absorbs each other called harmony. Every element, event, piece of event, tool in a work of art is always serves a specific purpose, acquires a logical connection and harmony with each other, both in form and content.

Thus the composition-work content is a formal element that ensures its complete transformation. Skillful of this element use i.e. direct it to a specific goal, of course, the creative laboratory of each artist helps in research. It is known that the composition of the work is a product of creation, just like the human body its dominance over every element, which affects as it surrounds the blood vessels will be the power. 3 (p. 65) The contradictions in life are as sharp and calm as the artistic conflict also have different views. They are also in the form of an open struggle between the heroes, the characters are also manifested in the form of their own voluntary struggles. Also artistic the conflict will be expressed in a unique way in each literary type and genre. In drama (comedy, tragedy, play) appears in a completely different way in his works. In general, everyone is perfect how the work of art makes its elements such as conflict, form and subject, content and idea regardless of its manifestation, it impressively reflected a particular aspect of life, is the beauty created by the creator. The inner and outer world of a work of art is its structure, the location of the events in the plot, from the set of characters and the relationships between them consists of. This phenomenon is called composition. Since the law of the playwright's creativity When we dwell on the rules, we must first mention the term plot.

DISCUSSION

The plot is French is "plot," meaning "thing, content, subject." The content of the work, the connection between the protagonists, the system of relationships is the plot. The plot itself is also a series consisting of parts: exposition, node, course of events, culmination and solution. However the subjects differ from each other in their structure, the way they are manifested. Works of art the term “fabula” also occurs in some studies where the composition has been analyzed. Fabula derived from the Latin word “fabula” which means to tell a parable. Fiction work means the vital material on which the work is based. Elements of the plot among which it is permissible to comment first on what the exposition is. The exposition is Latin derived from the word "expositio," meaning "to explain." Venue, the social landscape of the period, the place where the heroes grew up, the conditions of the environment, and so on called exposure. The exposition can be anywhere in the work. Subject another element is the node of events. The knot is often the first meeting of the heroes or arises due to a dispute over a serious problem. The knot of events defines, actively moves the heroes. The knot of events is only between the heroes rather, it may also be related to the protagonist’s own thoughts.

This condition is also considered a node. When the knot of events occurs, it somehow grows and develops goes The process of development of events in a plot after a certain node is called event development. The knot may seem to occur suddenly. But the course of events is long process. Various confusions also occur in the course of events. For example Abdulla The relationship between Homid Otabek and Silver in Qadiri’s novel The Last Days does various tricks to break. Because of his evils, the heroes are incredible becomes difficult. These are the

new nodes that emerged during the course of the plot or confusions are called perepetia. Any contradictions and disagreements are gradual rises to the highest peak. This fact of life is the events in the subject of the work of art is also suitable for development. Because the confrontation between the heroes is also growing, most of its own rises to a high level. They are the culmination of the work's subject matter. We can see in the texts that there are many contradictions for the humanist. In the analysis of subjects an understanding of the truth occurs by identifying the causes of the conflicts. Badiiy The reflection of conflicts and struggles in the literature is carried out through artistic means is increased. The character of the main protagonists rises to the top of the events in the plot of the work the episode that shows the image, the culmination of the events, the plot events and the protagonists the episode that embodies the decision of destiny is called the solution. Exposition, node, the course of events, the culmination and the solution are the connecting parts that make up the subject is Together, they define the significance of the work. The composition of the subject of the work There are two other elements that are not included, but are related to it, one of which is the preface, the second is the arrival. In the introduction, the author informs the reader of the purpose of his work gives explanations about. At the end, the plot of the heroes' work is over is the part that informs about the destiny after. (4. 34, 35,36.b). "Literature and The development of art and culture is the key to raising the spiritual world of our people (Shavkat Mirziyoyev). Based on a certain idea by the playwright the birth, development of the work for staging, its peculiarities, types, to him the requirements are understood as the skill of the playwright.

So of the drama To study the stages of its emergence on a global scale, the historian of its history, it is advisable to consult the opinions of art historians and experts in the field (5. 3) In the second decade of independence, our drama developed rapidly began. There have been major changes in dramaturgy and directing. Created history and glorification of man in works on modern themes, love and devotion to the Motherland, ideas of respect for our values are reflected in artistic ideas (6.181). "There are also a lot of works on straight social themes, in which the predominance of ideas is also felt. Events that serve the development of society, have a negative impact on people's minds, It is good that the story of the fight against the events is shown, it is presented to the audience, but the discussions, that is, the reviews of the works, are very little published, unfortunately, today has become one of the problems of the day "(6.49).

CONCLUSIONS

Dramaturgy always appeals to man, seeks to reveal the secrets of his soul, humane tries to understand the essence of the relationship, whether the person is historical or modern does not matter. In the future, for our young artists to skillfully shake the pen it should be possible now. Establishment of creative centers in each district center, in music schools, cultural centers, young writers' clubs are constantly activity, which of course inspires every creator, encourages hard work and the day will come from which royal works are bound to emerge.

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